

Supplementary Document

APPENDIX: PROOF OF THEOREM 1

The proof consists of two steps. Firstly we prove that the modified DCBA framework converges to a fixed point. Then we prove that the fixed point is the optimal solution of the optimization problem (15).

A. Proof of convergence

1) Proof without considering DG inequality constraints

Firstly, the relationship between $\Delta P_t^{ns} = P_t^{ns+1} - P_t^{ns}$ and λ_t, D_t is computed. Due to the existence of discontinuity, the optimal solution of the EG sub-problem is obtained on the boundary, thus the optimization of EG sub-problem can be converted to (A1) and $P_t^{ns,e}$ satisfies (A2).

$$P_t^{ns,e} = \arg \min \left\{ (p_t - \lambda_t^{ns,e}) P_t^e + f_t^e(P_t^e) \right\}$$

$$f_t^e(P_t^e) = \omega^e \left(-\frac{(p_t - \lambda_t^e)}{|p_t - \lambda_t^e|} \kappa_t^{e,e} P_{\max}^e - P_t^e \right) + \frac{1}{\rho^e} \left\| -\frac{(p_t - \lambda_t^e)}{|p_t - \lambda_t^e|} \kappa_t^{e,e} P_{\max}^e - P_t^e \right\|_2^2 \quad (\text{A1})$$

$$\left(p_t - \lambda_t^{ns,e} \right) + \frac{\partial f_t^e(P_t^e)}{\partial P_t^e} \Bigg|_{P_t^{ns,e}} = 0 \quad (\text{A2})$$

where ω^e is the Lagrangian multiplier and $\rho^e \in (0, \bar{\rho})$ is the pre-specified penalty parameter [36].

Following the same steps, $P_t^{ns+1,e}$ satisfies (A3), and we use the first order Taylor expansion of $\frac{\partial f_t^e(P_t^e)}{\partial P_t^e} \Bigg|_{P_t^{ns+1,e}}$ at $P_t^{ns,e}$ to analyze the dynamics around the fixed point [28], as shown in (A4).

$$\left(p_t - \lambda_t^{ns+1,e} \right) + \frac{\partial f_t^e(P_t^e)}{\partial P_t^e} \Bigg|_{P_t^{ns+1,e}} = 0 \quad (\text{A3})$$

$$\left(p_t - \lambda_t^{ns+1,e} \right) + \frac{\partial f_t^e(P_t^e)}{\partial P_t^e} \Bigg|_{P_t^{ns,e}} + \frac{\partial^2 f_t^e(P_t^e)}{\partial^2 P_t^e} \Bigg|_{P_t^{ns,e}} \times \Delta P_t^{ns,e} = 0 \quad (\text{A4})$$

According to (A1)-(A4), equation (A5) is obtained:

$$\Delta P_t^{ns,e} = \frac{\rho^e}{2} (\lambda_t^{ns+1,e} - \lambda_t^{ns,e}) \quad (\text{A5})$$

Going through similar analysis as EG, $\Delta P_t^{ns,w}, \Delta P_t^{ns,s}$, and $\Delta P_t^{ns,g}$ are computed by (A6)-(A8).

$$\Delta P_t^{ns,w} = \frac{\rho^w}{2} (\lambda_t^{ns+1,w} - \lambda_t^{ns,w}) \quad (\text{A6})$$

$$\Delta P_t^{ns,s} = \frac{\rho^s}{2} (\lambda_t^{ns+1,s} - \lambda_t^{ns,s}) \quad (\text{A7})$$

$$\Delta P_t^{ns,g} = \frac{\lambda^{ns+1,g} - \lambda^{ns,g}}{2a^g} \quad (\text{A8})$$

The analysis of BES is shown as follows:

If we do not use the piece-wise linear (PWL) function to approximate the value function, the optimal solution of the BES sub-problem can be computed by (A9) (Without considering inequality constraints).

$$P_t^{ns,b} = \arg \min \left\{ \bar{V}_t^{b,x}(SOC_t^{b,x}) - \lambda_t^{ns,b} P_t^b \right\} = \arg \min \left\{ \bar{V}_t^{b,x}(SOC_t^b - P_t^b) - \lambda_t^{ns,b} P_t^b \right\} \quad (\text{A9})$$

Therefore, $\Delta P_t^{ns,b}$ can be computed by (A10).

$$\Delta P_t^{ns,b} = \left(\frac{\partial^2 (\bar{V}_t^{b,x}(SOC_t^b - P_t^b) + f_t^b(P_t^b))}{\partial^2 P_t^b} \Bigg|_{P_t^{ns,b}} \right)^{-1} (\lambda_t^{ns+1,b} - \lambda_t^{ns,b}) \quad (\text{A10})$$

According to the Bellman optimality principle (13), $\bar{V}_t^{b,x}(SOC_t^{b,x}) = \sum_{t+\Delta t}^T C_t(\mathbf{S}_t, \mathbf{x}_t)$, thus $\bar{V}_t^{b,x}(SOC_t^{b,x})$ is a quadratic function with the positive quadratic coefficient. Assume that $\left. \frac{\partial^2 (\bar{V}_t^{b,x}(SOC_t^b - P_t^b) + f_t^b(P_t^b))}{\partial^2 P_t^b} \right|_{P_t^{ns,b}} = v_t^b > 0$, $\Delta P_t^{ns,b}$ can be computed by (A11).

$$\Delta P_t^{ns,b} = \frac{(\lambda_t^{ns+1,b} - \lambda_t^{ns,b})}{v_t^b} \quad (\text{A11})$$

If we use the PWL function to approximate the value function, the optimal solution of the BES sub-problem can be computed by (A12) (With considering inequality constraints).

$$\begin{aligned} P_t^{ns,b} &= \arg \min \left\{ \sum_{m=1}^M v_{m,t}^{b,x} SOC_{m,t}^{b,x} - \lambda_t^{ns,b} P_t^b + f_t^b(P_t^b) \right\} \\ f_t^b(P_t^b) &= \omega^e \left(\frac{(v_{m',t}^{b,x} + \lambda_t^b)}{|v_{m',t}^{b,x} + \lambda_t^b|} \kappa_t^{b,b} P_{\max}^b - P_t^b \right) + \frac{1}{\rho^b} \left\| \frac{(v_{m',t}^{b,x} + \lambda_t^b)}{|v_{m',t}^{b,x} + \lambda_t^b|} \kappa_t^{b,b} P_{\max}^b - P_t^b \right\|_2^2 \\ \sum_{m=1}^M SOC_{m,t}^{b,x} &= SOC_t^b - P_t^b \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A12})$$

Therefore, $P_t^{ns,b}$ satisfies (A13). Going through the similar analysis as EG, $\Delta P_t^{ns,b}$ can be computed by (A14).

$$-v_{m',t}^{b,x} - \lambda_t^{ns,b} + \frac{\partial f_t^b(P_t^b)}{\partial P_t^b} \Big|_{P_t^{ns,b}} = 0 \quad (\text{A13})$$

$$\Delta P_t^{ns,b} = \frac{\rho^b}{2} (\lambda_t^{ns+1,b} - \lambda_t^{ns,b}) \quad (\text{A14})$$

Whether we use PWL function to approximate the value function or not, $\Delta P_t^{ns,b}$ is equal to a positive parameter multiplying $(\lambda_t^{ns+1,b} - \lambda_t^{ns,b})$. In the following analysis, we apply the condition that uses the PWL function to approximate the value function.

Based on the above analysis, the relationship between ΔP_t^{ns} and λ_t can be computed by (A15).

$$\Delta P_t^{ns} = \mathbf{E} (\lambda_t^{ns+1} - \lambda_t^{ns}), \mathbf{E} = \text{diag} \left[\frac{1}{2a^g}; \frac{\rho^e}{2}; \frac{\rho^w}{2}; 0; \frac{\rho^s}{2}; \frac{\rho^b}{2} \right] \quad (\text{A15})$$

Then we can formulate the modified DCBA framework into the compact matrix form:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{H}^{ns+1} &= \tilde{\mathbf{V}} \mathbf{H}^{ns} \\ \mathbf{H}^{ns} &= \begin{bmatrix} \lambda_t^{ns} \\ \kappa_t^{e,ns} \\ \kappa_t^{w,ns} \\ \kappa_t^{s,ns} \\ \kappa_t^{b,ns} \\ \mathbf{D}_t^{ns} \end{bmatrix}, \tilde{\mathbf{V}} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{A} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \epsilon_\lambda \mathbf{I} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{A} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \epsilon_\kappa^e \mathbf{I}_e \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{A} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \epsilon_\kappa^w \mathbf{I}_w \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{A} & \mathbf{0} & \epsilon_\kappa^s \mathbf{I}_s \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{A} & \epsilon_\kappa^b \mathbf{I}_b \\ \mathbf{E}(\mathbf{I}-\mathbf{A}) & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & (\mathbf{A}-\epsilon_\lambda \mathbf{E}) \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A16})$$

where $\epsilon_\lambda = \varepsilon_\lambda \mathbf{I}$.

Further, we reformulate $\tilde{\mathbf{V}}$ into a non-negative matrix $\mathbf{V}$ plus a perturbation matrix $\Delta \mathbf{V}$ influenced by parameters $\epsilon = [\epsilon_\lambda, \epsilon_\kappa^e, \epsilon_\kappa^w, \epsilon_\kappa^s, \epsilon_\kappa^b]$ to analyze the property of $\tilde{\mathbf{V}}$:

$$\tilde{V} = V + \Delta V$$

$$V = \begin{bmatrix} A & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & A & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & A & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & A & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & A & 0 \\ E(I-A) & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & A \end{bmatrix}, \Delta V = \begin{bmatrix} \epsilon_\lambda I \\ \epsilon_\kappa^e I_e \\ \epsilon_\kappa^w I_w \\ \epsilon_\kappa^s I_s \\ \epsilon_\kappa^b I_b \\ -\epsilon_\lambda E \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{A17})$$

Since V is a lower block triangular matrix and A is the diagonal element, the eigenvalues of V are the same as that of A . Since the communication matrix A is irreducible, 1 is the simple eigenvalue of A and the others have moduli smaller than 1. Therefore, $\phi_1 = \phi_2 \dots = \phi_6 = 1$ is the semi-simple repeated eigenvalue of V and the other eigenvalues have moduli smaller than 1. Let u^T , w be the left and right eigenvectors of V corresponding to eigenvalue 1, we construct the matrix U^T , W by (A18) and (A19). It can be verified that $U^T W = I$.

$$U^T = [u_1^T; u_2^T; u_3^T; u_4^T; u_5^T; u_6^T] = \begin{bmatrix} I^T E & 0^T & 0^T & 0^T & 0^T & I^T \\ 0^T & 0^T & 0^T & 0^T & I^T & 0^T \\ 0^T & 0^T & 0^T & I^T & 0^T & 0^T \\ 0^T & 0^T & I^T & 0^T & 0^T & 0^T \\ 0^T & I^T & 0^T & 0^T & 0^T & 0^T \\ I^T & 0^T & 0^T & 0^T & 0^T & 0^T \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{A18})$$

$$W = [w_1, w_2, w_3, w_4, w_5, w_6] = \frac{1}{I} \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & I \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & I & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & I & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & I & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & I & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ I & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\sum_{i \in I} E^{i,i} I \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{A19})$$

Based on Lemma 1 in [37], Proposition 1 in [21] and [32], we can compute the corresponding matrix by (A20), and thus we can obtain that the eigenvalues of matrix satisfy (A21). Therefore, we can obtain that there exists a small ϵ such that $\phi_1(\epsilon) = \phi_2(\epsilon) \dots = \phi_5(\epsilon) = 1$, and the other eigenvalues have moduli smaller than 1.

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sum_{i=1}^I U_1^T \frac{\partial \tilde{V}}{\partial \epsilon^i} W_1 & \dots & \sum_{i=1}^I U_1^T \frac{\partial \tilde{V}}{\partial \epsilon^i} W_I \\ \dots & \dots & \dots \\ \sum_{i=1}^I U_I^T \frac{\partial \tilde{V}}{\partial \epsilon^i} W_1 & \dots & \sum_{i=1}^I U_I^T \frac{\partial \tilde{V}}{\partial \epsilon^i} W_I \end{bmatrix} = \frac{1}{I} \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ I^T I_b & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\sum_{i \in I} E^{i,i} I^T I_b I \\ I^T I_s & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\sum_{i \in I} E^{i,i} I^T I_s I \\ I^T I_w & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\sum_{i \in I} E^{i,i} I^T I_w I \\ I^T I_e & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\sum_{i \in I} E^{i,i} I^T I_e I \\ I^T I & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\sum_{i \in I} E^{i,i} I^T I I \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{A20})$$

$$\frac{\partial \phi_i(\epsilon)}{\partial \epsilon} = 0, i = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5$$

$$\frac{\partial \phi_6(\epsilon)}{\partial \epsilon} = -\sum_{i \in I} E^{i,i} \quad (\text{A21})$$

Next, the convergence of the proposed modified DCBA framework is proved. We reformulate (A16) as (A22) based on the difference theory.

$$H^{ns} = \tilde{V} H^{ns-1} = \tilde{V}^{ns} H^0 = a_1 \phi_1(\epsilon)^{ns} b_1 + \dots + a_{6l} \phi_{6l}(\epsilon)^{ns} b_{6l} \quad (\text{A22})$$

where $\mathbf{b}=[\mathbf{b}_1, \mathbf{b}_2, \dots, \mathbf{b}_{6l}]$ are the eigenvectors of $\tilde{\mathbf{V}}$ and $\mathbf{b}_1=[\mathbf{I}; \mathbf{0}; \mathbf{0}; \mathbf{0}; \mathbf{0}; \mathbf{0}]$, $\mathbf{b}_2=[\mathbf{0}; \mathbf{I}; \mathbf{0}; \mathbf{0}; \mathbf{0}; \mathbf{0}]$, $\mathbf{b}_3=[\mathbf{0}; \mathbf{0}; \mathbf{I}; \mathbf{0}; \mathbf{0}; \mathbf{0}]$, $\mathbf{b}_4=[\mathbf{0}; \mathbf{0}; \mathbf{0}; \mathbf{I}; \mathbf{0}; \mathbf{0}]$, $\mathbf{b}_5=[\mathbf{0}; \mathbf{0}; \mathbf{0}; \mathbf{0}; \mathbf{I}; \mathbf{0}]$. $a_i = \mathbf{b}^{-1} \mathbf{H}^0$ are constant coefficients.

Since $\phi_1(\epsilon) = \phi_2(\epsilon) \dots = \phi_5(\epsilon) = 1$ and the other eigenvalues have moduli smaller than 1, we can obtain that $\mathbf{H}^{ns}$ converges to span $[\mathbf{I}^T, \mathbf{I}^T, \mathbf{I}^T, \mathbf{I}^T, \mathbf{I}^T, \mathbf{0}^T]^T$ when $ns \rightarrow \infty$, which proves that the proposed modified DCBA framework converges to a fixed point.

2) Proof with considering DG inequality constraints

Based on the analysis in [21][32], if P_t^g is saturated, $\Delta P_t^g = 0$. Therefore, the corresponding matrix $\mathbf{E}$ should be changed to $\tilde{\mathbf{E}}$. The definition of matrix $\tilde{\mathbf{E}}$ is shown in (A23).

$$\tilde{E}^{i,i} = \begin{cases} E^{i,i}, & \text{if } P_t^g \text{ is not saturated} \\ 0, & \text{if } P_t^g \text{ is saturated} \end{cases} \quad (\text{A23})$$

Following the similar eigenvalue perturbation analysis in 1), the proposed modified DCBA framework can converge to a fixed point when ϵ is small enough.

B. Proof of optimality

It is easy to see that the real-time ED model of MG in this paper is a convex optimization problem. Based on the convex optimization theory [38], the KKT conditions are sufficient for the points to be primal and dual optimal. Next, we prove that the fixed point satisfies the KKT conditions of the real-time ED model of MG.

The optimization model can be formulated by (A24).

$$\begin{aligned} \text{minimize } & J_t(\mathbf{x}_t) = \min \left\{ C_t(\mathcal{S}_t, \mathbf{x}_t) + \sum_{b \in \mathbf{B}} \bar{V}_t^{b,x} (SOC_t^{b,x}) \right\} \\ \text{subject to } & eq_t(\mathbf{x}_t) = 0 \\ & ieq_t(\mathbf{x}_t) \leq 0 \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A24})$$

where eq_t represents the equality constraints (i.e. (3) and (10) in the main manuscript), and ieq_t represents the inequality constraints (i.e. (4)-(9), (11) in the main manuscript).

We define the Lagrangian function associated with (A24) as (A25).

$$L(\mathbf{x}_t, \lambda, \gamma, \mu) = J_t(\mathbf{x}_t) + \lambda eq_t^1(\mathbf{x}_t) + \gamma eq_t^2(\mathbf{x}_t) + \sum_{i=1}^{14} \mu^i ieq_t^i(\mathbf{x}_t) \quad (\text{A25})$$

where eq_t^1 is related to (3) and eq_t^2 is related to (10). $ieq_t^{1,2}$ are related to (4), $ieq_t^{3,4}$ are related to (5), $ieq_t^{5,6}$ are related to (6), $ieq_t^{7,8}$ are related to (7), $ieq_t^{9,10}$ are related to (8), $ieq_t^{11,12}$ are related to (9), and $ieq_t^{13,14}$ are related to (11).

The KKT conditions are shown in (A26).

$$\begin{cases} \nabla L = \nabla J_t(\mathbf{x}_t^*) + \lambda \nabla eq_t^1(\mathbf{x}_t^*) + \gamma \nabla eq_t^2(\mathbf{x}_t^*) + \sum_{i=1}^{14} \mu^i \nabla ieq_t^i(\mathbf{x}_t^*) = 0 \\ eq_t^i(\mathbf{x}_t^*) = 0, i = 1, 2 \\ ieq_t^i(\mathbf{x}_t^*) \leq 0, i = 1, 2, \dots, 14 \\ \mu^i ieq_t^i(\mathbf{x}_t^*) = 0, i = 1, 2, \dots, 14 \\ \mu^i \geq 0, i = 1, 2, \dots, 14 \end{cases} \quad (\text{A26})$$

For sub-problem (16), the KKT conditions $ieq_t^i \leq 0, \mu^i ieq_t^i = 0, \mu^i \geq 0; i = 1, 2, 3, 4$ and $\nabla L^g = 0, \mathbf{x}_t = P_t^g$ are satisfied. For sub-problem (27), since $0 \leq \kappa_t^{e,e} \leq 1$, the KKT conditions $ieq_t^i \leq 0, \mu^i ieq_t^i = 0, \mu^i \geq 0; i = 5, 6$ and $\nabla L^e = 0, \mathbf{x}_t = P_t^e$ are satisfied. For sub-problem (28), the KKT conditions $ieq_t^i \leq 0, \mu^i ieq_t^i = 0, \mu^i \geq 0; i = 7, 8$ and $\nabla L^w = 0, \mathbf{x}_t = P_t^w$ are satisfied. For sub-problem (29), the KKT conditions $ieq_t^i \leq 0, \mu^i ieq_t^i = 0, \mu^i \geq 0; i = 9, 10$ and $\nabla L^s = 0, \mathbf{x}_t = P_t^s$ are satisfied. For sub-problem (30), the KKT conditions $ieq_t^i \leq 0, \mu^i ieq_t^i = 0, \mu^i \geq 0; i = 11, 12, 13, 14$, $eq_t^2 = 0$ and

$\nabla L^b = 0, x_t = P_t^b$ are satisfied. Therefore, $\nabla L = \nabla L^g + \nabla L^e + \nabla L^w + \nabla L^s + \nabla L^b = 0$ are satisfied.

Then, since A is a doubly stochastic matrix, we can obtain that $AI=I$ and $I^T A = I^T$. According to (22), we can obtain (A27).

$$\begin{aligned}
I^T D_t^{ns+1} &= I^T A D_t^{ns} - I^T (P_t^{ns+1} - P_t^{ns}) \\
&= I^T D_t^{ns} - I^T (P_t^{ns+1} - P_t^{ns}) \\
&\rightarrow I^T (D_t^{ns+1} + P_t^{ns+1}) = I^T (D_t^{ns} + P_t^{ns}) = \dots = I^T (D_t^0 + P_t^0)
\end{aligned} \tag{A27}$$

According to the previous proof, $D_t^{ns} = 0$ when $ns \rightarrow \infty$. According to (21), we can obtain that $\sum_{i \in I} P_i^0 = l_i$. Therefore, $\sum_{i \in I} P_i^{ns} = l_i, ns \rightarrow 0$. The KKT conditions $eq_i^1 = 0$ is satisfied.

Finally, we can obtain that the fixed point of the proposed modified DCBA framework satisfies the KKT conditions of the optimization model. Thus the fixed point is the optimal solution of the real-time ED model of MG.

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